

ART STUDIES

THE SPECIFIC APPLICATION AND PRACTICE OF PERCUSSION INSTRUMENTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF WESTERN ORCHESTRAS

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Abstract

Percussion instruments, as one of the oldest and most diverse instruments in the music world, have a development history full of the imprints of human civilization. From ancient times, humans have been producing rhythms and conveying messages by striking their bodies or stones, which can be regarded as the rudimentary form of percussion music. With the progress of civilization and the development of music, percussion instruments gradually became one of the earliest types of playing instruments.

Keywords: percussion instruments, development history, thesis design, teaching.

In China, the history of percussion instruments can be traced back to the Neolithic Age, when various primitive percussion instruments such as earth drums, pottery bells, pottery chimes, and stone chimes were invented, primarily used in daily labor. By the Bronze Age, percussion instruments like chime bells had attained a high historical status, becoming an integral part of courtly music. Most of these instruments were played in ensembles with wind instruments, forming a unique "gong and drum music".

In Europe, the development of percussion instruments also has a long history. However, it was not until about 450 years ago that percussion was officially incorporated into symphony orchestras. Initially, this integration was primarily aimed at simulating sound effects and stimulating the audience with a loud sound. With continuous exploration and innovation by musicians, more and more percussion instruments were added to orchestras, such as timpani and cymbals. Especially the timpani, as one of the most important percussion instruments in the orchestra, is even hailed as the "second conductor of the orchestra".

However, the development of percussion instruments has not been smooth sailing. Before 1982, the development of Western percussion music in China was relatively slow. However, with the deepening of reform and opening up, foreign performers and professors came to China one after another, bringing new concepts and methods to the Chinese percussion community, as well as a large number of new musical scores. Since then, the cause of Chinese percussion music has flourished, and higher music institutions such as the Central Conservatory of Music have become home to the largest collection of percussion scores in the world.

Entering the 21st century, the development of percussion instruments has become more diversified. On the one hand, traditional ethnic percussion instruments have undergone continuous innovation in inheritance, resulting in the emergence of many excellent works and performance forms. On the other hand, with the exchange of globalized cultures, Western percussion instruments have also been widely used in Chinese ethnic

orchestras, forming a unique style that combines Chinese and Western elements. In addition, the emergence of electronic percussion instruments has injected new vitality into the development of percussion instruments.

Throughout the development of percussion instruments, numerous outstanding artists and performers have made significant contributions. For instance, Siegfried Fink from Germany is not only a renowned percussionist and composer but also an exceptional educator. Under his guidance, the Percussion Studio in Würzburg has become one of the most renowned percussion schools in the world. In China, percussionists like Zhang Jingli have also made great contributions to elevating the status of percussion music in both Chinese and international music circles through their own efforts.

Nowadays, percussion instruments have evolved into a vast family of instruments with a wide variety of types and diverse styles. Whether it's traditional gong and drum music or modern symphony and electronic music, percussion instruments have added endless colors to the music world with their unique charm. With the continuous progress of technology and the continuous development of human civilization, it is believed that percussion instruments will shine even brighter on the future music stage.

Paper Design

1. Introduction and research background introduction:

Briefly describe the development process of percussion instruments in the history of music.

Elucidate the significance of percussion instruments in modern music, particularly their evolving role within Western orchestras.

Propose a research question: How can percussion instruments be specifically applied and practiced in the construction of Western orchestras?

Research background:

Analyze the current research status of the role of percussion instruments in orchestras in the academic community.

Point out the research gaps and practical significance, such as technological innovation, changes in orchestra orchestration, etc.

Discuss the necessity of research, such as promoting the exchange and development of music culture, enhancing the performance level of orchestras, etc.

2. Overview of types of percussion instruments

Definition and classification:

Percussion instruments can be categorized into several major types based on their playing methods, timbre characteristics, and purposes, such as keyboard percussion instruments (piano, marimba), membrane percussion instruments (drums), and metal percussion instruments (cymbals, triangles), among others.

Briefly describe the origins, historical development, and applications of various types of musical instruments in modern music.

Characteristic analysis:

Discuss the timbre characteristics, playing techniques, and their roles in musical expression of various percussion instruments.

Analyze how different instruments collaborate with other vocal parts in an orchestra to achieve harmony and rhythm unity.

3. Analysis of the composition of an orchestra

Tradition and modernity:

Outline the traditional composition of an orchestra, including string, woodwind, brass, and percussion sections.

Discuss the changes in the composition of modern orchestras, especially the expansion and diversification of the percussion section.

Voice function and role:

Analyze the role of each vocal part in the orchestra, as well as how percussion instruments fill in the tonal gaps and enhance the rhythmic feel in different works.

Explore the dual role of percussion instruments as both coloristic and functional instruments.

4. Current application status of percussion instruments

Embodiment in musical works:

List and analyze the use of percussion instruments in specific works by composers such as Beethoven, Stravinsky, Prokofiev, and others.

Discuss the role of percussion instruments in different styles (classical, romantic, modern) and genres (symphony, concerto, chamber music).

Modern orchestra practice:

Analyze how contemporary renowned orchestras, such as the Berlin Philharmonic and the New York Philharmonic, arrange percussion instruments.

Explore the trend of percussion instruments becoming increasingly important in modern symphony orchestras and the reasons behind it.

5. Analysis and research on practical cases

Case analysis 1: Select a specific work and conduct a detailed analysis of the role, technical requirements, and performance techniques of percussion instruments in it.

Case analysis 2: Compare the differences in percussion instruments between different versions of the

same work (historical recordings and modern recordings), and explore the reasons for their evolution.

Case study 3: Investigate how a certain conductor or composer innovatively employs percussion instruments to breathe new life into their compositions.

6. Discussion on Technology and Expression Techniques technological innovation

Explore the application of modern electronic percussion instruments, ambient sound effects equipment, and other technological means in orchestras.

Analyze how these new technologies expand the expressiveness and possibilities of percussion instruments.

Expression technique:

Study the unique expressive ways of percussion instruments in different musical moods (such as cheerful, solemn, tense, etc.).

Discuss how percussion instruments can create contrast or integration with other vocal parts in the orchestra through changes in rhythm, tone color, and intensity.

7. Impact on orchestra construction

Team building:

Analyze the impact of adding percussionists to an orchestra on its overall performance, including skill complementarity and collaborative abilities.

Explore ways to enhance the training and team building of percussionists, in order to promote overall harmony within the orchestra.

Innovation and diversity of works:

Discuss the role of percussion instruments in promoting innovation in musical works, such as facilitating the emergence of new styles and expanding the scope of musical genres.

Analyze how percussion instruments can assist orchestras in achieving musical diversity and attracting a broader audience.

8. Conclusion and Suggestions for Future Research

Conclusion:

Summarize the main findings regarding the specific application and practice of percussion instruments in the construction of Western orchestras.

Emphasize the indispensable role of percussion instruments in modern music and their positive impact on the future development of orchestras.

Prospect and suggestions:

Suggest directions for future research, such as exploring in greater depth the fusion and innovation of percussion instruments in different cultural backgrounds.

Put forward improvement suggestions for orchestra management and education systems, aiming to promote the inheritance and development of percussion instrument art.

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